

Reflective critiques report

Subject:

BM5102 - Organisational behaviour

Lecturer:

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Introduction

Background/Context of Reflection

I've always wanted to do some research papers, investigation, site visit etc specifically in academia. Born in a family where both parents used to be teachers have definitely impacted me until now. I can proudly say the most priority in my family is education rather than a marriage.

When I was doing a degree in accounting and finance at the laksamana college of business (LCB) under accreditation of University of Chester UK, i didn't get a chance to do final year thesis or report as due to lack of researchers or supervisors in LCB forcing the management to pull the thesis out and replace it with small scale assignments and all exams throughout the modules. I knew that's going to happen as degree studies in LCB is quite fresh and there is development needed. Because of this I often get demotivated as my ambition in academics is to pursue the highest education system that I could get which is Phd before my 30s. With a solid foundation of know-how-to research is fundamental skills to get into the next stage. Some people may say 'Education is not something to be rushed, you have to enjoy the journey'. I couldn't agree more with the statement however, i believe each one of us have different approaches reflecting their own education based on their age. I've rushed to finish up my studies to an extent that I know in the later age my brain will not be as good as it used to be now.

I learned from my cousin who got her phd in mechanical engineering back in 2018 from Newcastle and currently working in UTB. During her study, she was diagnosed with an rare uncommon disease that affected her nerve system and her eyes were later found due to an impact of overworking brain and continuously seeing the computer's screen. She inspired me that "life is too short to not pursue what we're love" and indeed those words have inspired and still vivid to me. Based on this real experience I have, Health is the next essential aspect that I am looking forward to, it is important for both physically and emotionally healthy especially for a student who requires their brain and body to perform more effectively. I feel so helpless whenever I get sick particularly during this master study, where it demands my time commitment and we get a bunch of things to do every single week from every module taken. I definitely can't afford to get sick

Thesis statement:

In our group case study of organisational behaviour, three of us were cracking our heads struggling to choose an impactful research which is associated with the current pandemic. It is not until one of the group members went to the hospital to visit their family who got admitted and somehow overheard the nurses chatting about their working pattern during Covid-19. Therefore, we've decided to make Nurse as our research subject and the mental health issue came in a piece in conjunction with World mental health issues celebrated every 10th october. The research titles The impact of the pandemic COVID-19, on nurses' mental health and their organization's coping strategy management. In research we combined those subjects into Nurse

+ mental health issue + covid-19 into the google and the result is shocking. In late April the International Council of Nurses (ICN) already reported that “there is strong evidence that nurses are experiencing unprecedented levels of stress,” going on to say that nurses are at “high-risk for full-blown stress response syndromes, anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, chronic illness and burnout” (Ford, 2020). Moreover, there are already several reviews conducted on healthcare workers’ mental health in the pandemic of covid-19 with search dates up to May 2020; there are thirteen studies also been identified (Pappa et., 2020). Previously, I’ve visited the hospital before the pandemic for my father who was admitted due to severe abdominal pain. I always complain to the A&E desk asking why the services were slow and we have to wait for hours in the hospital. Badly, I have even posted on social media about the hospital services. The lack of healthcare workers in the hospital didn’t come to mind because I knew we have a lot of graduates from local healthcare institutes. I feel very angry and frustrated at the time.

However, those thoughts and angriness have been washed up recently when I started doing this research of nurses’ mental health. I feel empathy, sad at the same time, guilty for not looking after our health, and many more. I sort of crumbled inside and to be honest I cried. It is not something that the nurses wanted in the position in the first place. Even prior to the pandemic, research has studied the healthcare workers has already juggled shift pattern, holiday and rotational duties (West, S et al. 2009). With the pandemic, those systems triggered a sort of ‘quake’ that affected their emotional, psychological disorder, stress and well being and this impact in short and long term to patient care. I do even more respect the healthcare workers now, I enjoy seeing them working and taking care of patients, and I will give my full commitment in helping them in the future through my research. Suggestion for future study for this research is to gain empirical data from nurses and student nurses particularly in Brunei hospital and due to Covid-19 precautionary measures, the researchers cannot obtain their unique data and further observation.

This research has changed me a lot tremendously in respect to how I think and the small knowledge that we currently have. I gained the importance of research first before I speak. I feel so grateful to be grouped with Izzati and Asmad who studied from UBD for their bachelor. They gave me a lot of guidance in how to do research, formatting APA and rearranging into proper sentences. I don’t feel left out or alone in this activity, they were pretty entertaining my questions whenever i lost. To be honest i didn’t have a group project before during my bachelor, so working in the group fit is something new for me and i’m thrilled now we’ve nailed and able to finish it on time.

Second reflection that I would like to share here is on my individual analysis report. I feel so proud for this achievement and ability to bring this kind of research that is outside my forte and never done this before. The research named the use and perception of artificial intelligence (AI) in reducing recruitment bias, the idea came from the consequences of hiring wrong talent which will cost the business and the rising of job seekers’ disappointment upon rejection (Cappelli,

2019). The study didn't try to blame any parties in fact to just bring any unconscious bias from yourself up to the surface. Personally I like this research as it helps me to stay out of my comfort zone and to try new elements in my master of management. I always adore new technology such as robotics, machinery and AI, but I don't bear to study it as it sounds difficult and complicated. As I said early life is too short, therefore I decide to include AI and it is definitely worth it. From my behaviour upon working on this research, I can say that I am an adventurous person and keep myself open for challenges and that's what I like researching it just discovered truly about myself. Since AI study is unfamiliar for me, in a good way it forced me to read articles and journals to give understanding on what I am going to research on. I think that is the purpose of studying for a masters in university where you have to experiment and experience a lot of different techniques and skills guided by experts in their field. I'm totally making use of my time here in UBD.

One of things that I realized when I study masters here in UBD, that they are open to share a glimpse of projects and topics that they are working at the moment. Everyone is helping each other, the lecturers entertain you so much and still allow you to perform independent research. I feel great to be part of this society. It is not just an Organisation behaviour module but i think throughout the modules specifically to modules i have taken. I'm here not to brag or to gain extra points, but I'm the one who walks through the path so I know what and how it feels like. Furthermore, those research papers that i have working in group and single, had give me confident to continue this journey, ability to think beyond impossible and out-of-box, not afraid for being wrong etc., insightful study more than management field for example there is one research that i particularly working now is on global supply chain resilience and circular economy which i 'just' find it so interesting to discover. It definitely motivates and inspires me. Because of this positive energy, I am able to browse around the website of 'call for paper', research competition and many more platforms such as emerald publishing, elsevier etc. for researchers to display their research knowledge and ability to be professional.

People said Phd is a lonely journey, I argued it to be inconsistent because right now I already feel alone on this master journey. Due to pandemic, the learning adapted to an online which makes me feel low interaction with my colleagues and whenever i went to the university, i don't see crowded and i don't hear noises and this is one of the things that i missed so much. I can relate this aspect with Maslow need theory in social need where socialising and belongingness are why individuals prefer to work in groups and especially mature students (Haque et al., 2014). Without realising, i do need socialising with friends whom i can develop trust and be dependable to them. I take this reflective critiques report to the next level as it links our personal experience to research working to the master progression. It gives the opportunity to express yourself that you cannot right in an academic paper. It refreshes my intention to study master and what shape of career I want in the future.

Conclusion

In the early statement above, I did mention my interest is in researching and to pursue to next the level of education is definitely what I am aiming for and whether or not i will be a researcher or a lecturer is not decided yet. Obviously, the more educated we are, the better place we can get, so I don't rush putting myself into a working life. I still enjoy working as a master student and get to discover myself even more through this learning. Through our nurses' mental health issues research has taught me and my group about the importance of fact rather than emotional, read first then speak and many more. I display more smiles to the healthcare workers nowadays. I avoid prejudice and pre-bias thoughts. I do love researching even more and still looking forward for next semesters' research tasks

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